

ON PROBLEMS OF WASTEWATER AND ITS TREATMENT SYSTEM TERMS

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Abstract. It takes creative work and painstaking work to achieve clear meaning, compact form, easy and fluent pronunciation of terms and to ensure that each term is used in a single meaning and in a single form in one system. This article discusses some of the shortcomings of wastewater and its treatment system.

Key words: field terms, terminological dictionary, wastewater, dry matter, dried sediment, general sewage system.

Currently, although the general theoretical foundations of Uzbek scientific terminology have been developed, due to the complexity of creating scientific terms in national languages, the terms used in sources related to technology, including wastewater and its treatment, meet the requirements of scientific terminology. I cannot answer. Because industry experts are mainly technical experts, most of the lack of terms used in the wastewater and treatment process is related to their expression. In the creation of field terms, regardless of the structural structure of technical concepts, they are limited only by the intention (meaning) of its expression in our language. S.A. Chaplignin and D.S. Lotte also said about this: "The development of technology over the next few decades has created tens of thousands of terms. But most of these terms, it can be said, were created in violation of the "language norms" [5].

Creative work and painstaking work are required to achieve clear meaning, compact form, easy and fluent pronunciation of the terms and to ensure that each term is used in a single meaning and in a single form in one system. As the linguist scientist N.K. Sukhov said, "Creating a new national terminology is not only about translating certain terms from another language, but it is a work that requires real creativity" [2].

Today, terminological dictionaries and the regulation of the terminology of fields are considered to be one of the most important issues. For terminological dictionaries, it is necessary to choose a term, what the created or selected term should serve, correctly express a certain concept, be free of synonyms, and also correspond to the internal laws of the native language.

Some of the terms used in the lexicon of the Uzbek language, in particular, in its terminological system of wastewater and its treatment, are borrowed terms. Some terms related to the field have had several forms in the process of

being translated into Uzbek and used in the field. That is, there are cases of using several terms to express a single concept, expressing different concepts by means of one term, using two or more terms expressing the same concept with some morphological indicators changed. These manifestations are mostly found among the combined terms of wastewater terminology. For example, two-component compound terms such as dry residue / dried residue / dried sediment / dry matter express the concept of "the total amount of all undissolved substances in this water" in the field. The word belonging to the dry quality group in the compounds in the form of the qualifying adjective dry residue and dry substance is formed from the verb *kurimaq* on the basis of phonetic change, the word dry in the compound in the form of the qualifying adjective dry residue and dry sediment is based on the verb to dry - *gan* is formed by adding the suffixed adjective. The terms are connected by a conjunctive conjunction, and are distinguished by the fact that the subordinate word is expressed by an adjective and an adjective.

In the terminology of the field, the combined forms such as common sewage system/common drain sewage system/common drain system are also used. In industry sources, these terms are explained as follows.

A collective sewage system means that all sewage, that is, domestic, industrial and rainwater, is sent to the outside of the city through a single pipe to a treatment plant.

In the general drainage system, one sewage network is placed underground and all types of sewage are discharged together.

In the general heating system, various types of wastewater are discharged through a common network and cleaned in a treatment plant.

It can be seen from the comments given to the terms that it is known that different types of wastewater are combined around a common discharge scheme through one sewer pipe.

Umuqish sewage system is a complex compound term consisting of three components in the form of [subordinate word+ subordinate word+dominant word] connected in the adaptation method. One of the following words is represented by a compound word.

The general flow system combination is also an adaptive connection with a complex structure, made in the form [subordinate word+ subordinate word+dominant word]. This compound also has the above meaning.

In the two-component generalization system [subordinate word+dominant word], the subordinate word is represented by a compound word, and the form of the combination is more condensed.

From the above analysis, it can be seen that the content of the joint sewage system is more clearly and clearly expressed than other joints.

The terms total split system, total split discharge system, and total split sewage system are combined around the scheme of discharge of domestic and industrial wastewater separately, and atmospheric wastewater through separate networks. is different from That is, the same theme was expressed through terms with two different derivational structures.

Full undivided system and compound terms of full undivided system are distinguished by an adjective expressed by an undivided verb group. This system is a single sewer network, where dirty domestic and industrial wastewater is discharged, polluted industrial wastewater is first transferred to local treatment facilities.

We can also observe the above situations in compound terms such as incompletely separated sewage system and partially divided system.

A separate sewerage system consists of two sewerage networks, one of which discharges domestic and industrial wastewater, and the other discharges wastewater from precipitation.

In partially split systems, domestic and industrial wastewater is sent to a treatment plant through wastewater networks. Atmospheric wastewater is discharged into the basin through open ditches. This system is the most convenient from the sanitary point of view.

It can be seen from the comments given above that they are terms that have different structures and express the same meaning.

These shortcomings in the field are caused, first of all, by the fact that the authors use the expressive possibilities of the Uzbek language (words and affixes) without taking into account the direct translation of some terms. as a result, their meaning and structure are completely different for our language.

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